

A VIEW OF THE WHOLE THAT ECHOES THE TOTAL THEORY

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Abstract: The structure of the Whole is briefly described and is what TOTALITARIAN THEORY brings. There is a one-dimensional, two-dimensional and three-dimensional world of real dimensions. Behind them there are the imaginary space, but there are also the dimensions of time, real and imaginary. Simple motion determines the time Dt , which is the same in all three dimensions of a movement.

While space has three dimensions with the corresponding imaginary ones, time, as defined, has the three dimensions with the corresponding imaginary ones belonging to the goddess and so many others that belong to the ultimate reality. It is the world of 18 dimensions.

Finally, it remains to create the world of 24 dimensions, which will have in addition to the dimensions of the time of the goddess and which will have a distant zero and another six that will belong to the man who will become a creator

Keywords: Totalitarian Theory, real dimensions.

1. INTRODUCTION

We have formulated that hydrogen atoms consist of two rotating bubbles around their center of mass and consist of a thinner than the surrounding ether. Here we will see the densities and viscosity of the ether and other sizes, such as radius of bubbles.

We formulated the advanced form of TOTAL THEORY¹ that resonates in the worldview OF THE IDION, and here we will mathematicalize the theory, creating new mathematics. The ultimate, higher reality is the cause of the creation of worlds, and universes corresponding to these worlds. In our own world, after the goddess was born in the bowels of zero, she created our world. But the goddess also created other different worlds, the last of which did not work yet and human cooperation remains in this direction and this work is appropriate.

2. METHODOLOGY

This work adopts the methodology of TOTAL THEORY. There are principles, or doctrines, or other requests, or other axioms, to create the theory.

The basic doctrine is the unbornness of the ultimate if ever reality, the second doctrine is the self-birth of the Goddess.

The Whole has logical relevance, revealed by inductive reasoning, as well as abductive ones.

The Whole is dominated by determinism and the self-authority of man is the product of representations and the logic of man, whatever it may be.

THE NUMBERS

As you know, there are the natural numbers 1,2,3,4,... called positive integers.

There are both the negative integers and the zero, which are denoted, 0,-1,-2,-3,... And they arose from a solution of the equation $x+b=a$ and a,b , natural numbers. Natural and negative integers the set of integers.

¹ THE TOTAL THEORY, International Journal of Mathematics and Physical Sciences Research, Apr2020-Sept2020

There are also the rational numbers or fractions and they result from the solution of the equation $bx=a$, $x=a/b$, $b \neq 0$. The set of integers is a subset of the rational numbers.

There are also the unspoken numbers, such as $2^{1/2}=1.41423\dots$, and $\pi=2.14139\dots$, i.e. numbers that are not explicit (a/b).

The set of sayings and virtues are the real numbers. If we assign to a number an object, positive numbers reflect nature, matter, while negative numbers reflect non-matter, the intangible.

The equation $x^2 + 1=0$ is not solved by the above numbers and therefore it is necessary to enter the imaginary unit $(-1)^{1/2} = i=x$. The root of the negative real number -1, becomes the cause of the creation of imaginary numbers. And the complex numbers have the form, $z=x+iy$, and x,y are real numbers.

POLAR FORM OF COMPLEX NUMBERS

O y, -y is the axis of imaginary numbers and x, -x, the axis of the real numbers of Cartesian coordinates.

Complex numbers are vectors, and to x and to y form an angle θ as in the figure above. R= circle radius and sum of vectors x, y. Thus

$$x=R\cos\theta, y=R\sin\theta$$

$$z=x+iy=R(\cos\theta+isin\theta)$$

is the complex number in Cartesian and Polar coordinates.

As you can see, the Cartesian and Polar coordinates are at the level of x,y. That is, there is the one-dimensionality of space and the imaginary one-dimensionality of space, so it is a two-dimensional space corresponding to the complex number, consisting of vectors.

CREATION OF THE FIRST WORLD

As it was developed in TOTAL THEORY, with the imagination of the Goddess who imagined the distribution of infinite points, put into oscillation the infinitely distributed points of three-dimensional space, an infinite ether is born with a large bubble of sparse ether, which is the control center of the Whole. It's the one-dimensional world. As you know, the line extends to one dimension. In fact it is 4dimensional, because there is also the dimension of time that occurs in the same dimension of space and there is also the imaginary dimension of space and the other of time.

Logic is a way of being of zero. Which encloses in the infinite immaculate energy and the forces within it. One force is $F=-Cz$, and $z=R\cos(\omega t+\phi)$, it is the one-dimensional oscillation of F and its energy is, $E=Cx^2 =mv^2$. m is not the sphere mass of our world, but corresponds to the mass, and it is small bubbles ether in line, in radius R of the central bubble of the Whole, which thicken and dilute the parts of R with a frequency of ω .

This world is non-material because it happens entirely inside the central bubble. It is supplied with energy from the central oscillator small sphere of dense ether. At the north pole of positives z, it touches when the oscillation R radius of bubbles reaches there, in the oscillator².

² In the initial conception of the theory, it was considered that the oscillator It is the control center, small and located in the center of the central bubble, but located in the crust, at the north pole and the rhythms of the oscillations of the oscillations it transmits to the control center are programmed, by an individual computer.

Central spherical bubble with its center and north the oscillator small sphere itself that transmits its oscillation to the central small sphere of control of universes and on the crusty a flat-universe adjacent to the crust at the southern end. Any straight segment zB that leaves the oscillator and ends at level E at B e.g. , intersects the bark of the central bubble;

They are $z=1=R$, $(-z)=-R$ and $(-z)^2+1=0$ and $-z=i$. In this case, there is a real oscillation of R in the positive z and on the diameter $2R$, divided by ΔR and an oscillation imaginary, in the negative $-z$, $-R=1i$. We have already told you that the positives correspond to the real world and the imaginary to the negative, and here $+z=1=R$ corresponds to the real and the $-z=-R=1i$. The oscillation of the central bubble R of the real world, reaches the control center of the universes (central bubble), from where it is supplied with energy; the one-dimensional world is located on the coordinate axis z and with $R=z=1$ the oscillation radius of the real world and $-z=1i=-R$ the radius R is also of the oscillation of the imaginary world, which occurs in the imagination of the goddess face and in the storehouse of the way to exist in the distant zero!

The complex number $z=R+i(-R)=R(\cos\theta+i\cos(\theta+\pi))$. It corresponds to the polar coordinates of the one bias when the world is one-dimensional. But in reality it is three-dimensional, because there is also the dimension of the oscillation time and the imaginary radius.

THETWO-DIMENSIONAL WORLD OF SPACE WITH TIME

We have already mentioned that the complex numbers and their polar coordinates are two-dimensional, that is, they represent a plane. But the plane of space is identified by three points, which can be the vertices of a regular triangle. is located inside the central bubble; The radius of polar coordinates is a unit (1), as in the one-dimensional world.

De Moivre's theorem is,

$$z^n = \{R(\cos\theta + i\sin\theta)\}^n = R^n(\cos n\theta + i\sin n\theta)$$

If a number $w^n = z$, then the resulting root is,

$$z^{1/n} = \{R(\cos\theta + i\sin\theta)\}^{1/n} \\ = R^{1/n} \{ \cos[(\theta + 2k\pi)/n] + i\sin[(\theta + 2k\pi)/n] \}, k=1,2,3,\dots,n-1.$$

If only $z \neq 0$ then it has n different roots and z is of order n . The order n corresponds to the dimensions and dimensions in the two-dimensional world of space (circle, triangle), they are the two of space and the one-dimensional time, but also the two imaginary dimensions of space and the imaginary time, so $n=6$, ($z_y=x+iy$, $z_x=y+ix$, and the one-dimension Δt , from $x=x_0+v\Delta t$, $y=y_0+v\Delta t$, $x_i=x_{i0}+v\Delta t_i$, $y_i=y_{i0}+v\Delta t_i$). If we resolve as to Δt and Δt_i we find the real and imaginary dimension.

$$z = R(\cos 2k\pi/n + i\sin 2k\pi/n) = Re^{2k\pi i/n}, k=1,2,3,\dots,n-1,$$

If $z^n = 1$, $n=1,2,3,\dots$, is the equation of the whole that each of its world corresponds to one root n and not all the n in practice, then it has roots of order n of the unit and they are given by the relation, and $R=1$, the unitary circle, which we already assumed for the R of the central of a bubble.

The roots are $1, \omega, \omega^2, \omega^3, \dots, \omega^{n-1}$ and,

$$\omega = \cos 2\pi/n + i\sin 2\pi/n = e^{2\pi i/n}$$

Geometrically³ these roots represent the n vertices of regular polygons, such as the normal triangle that has the three vertices that determine the plane of space and is located within the central bubble. And $\omega = \cos 2\pi/6 + i \sin 2\pi/6$, corresponds to the normal triangle of space and its circle, the world of the two dimensions of space and time and the two imaginary dimensions of space and its imaginary time. But the two dimensions of the imaginary space, as we will see below, are condensed into one, so the world is 4-dimensional.

As in the one-dimensional world of space and here in the two-dimensional (and with time third dimension and the two imaginary dimensions), we will have surface waves, while in the one-dimensional we have radial, linear.

$$R = R_{x\text{with}} \cos(\omega t + \varphi),$$

x, z the plane of the circle in Cartesian coordinates; the waves are reflected in the cortex and returns the thickening to the center of the bubble. the force is $F = -CR_{xy}$ and the energy $E = m\omega^2 \pi R^2 \cos^2(\omega t + \varphi)$, where $m = \rho$ ether of the bubbles of the plane, corresponding to the mass of our own world. And the ether corresponds to a sparse mass, and the plane of this world, has a layer of bubbles flat and circular within the crust of the central bubble.

THE EQUALIZATION OF ALL WORLDS

The equation $z^n = 1$, is the equation of all worlds, deriving from the ultimate reality of zero. Every world derives from zero which is also a unit, and the root of z can reflect a world. $n=6$, while in the one-dimensional space of space there is the special regime that we have already described ($n=4$). One-dimensional and two-dimensional space of the worlds and time, are within the central bubble and there are infinite levels of circles that have a common diameter. the world of space is one, the distance could be infinite and all within the bubble. The two-dimensional real worlds of space are two, with common measures one on the z-axis and the other on the x intersecting. Working together, the potentially existing infinite dissociative worlds of space give volume waves to the sphere of the central bubble when coordinated. The waves are not only of the form of simple harmonic oscillation given, but also more complex.

At this point it must be said that worlds of more than eight ($n=12$) dimensions are located outside the central bubble and all have a seat adjacent to the spherical oscillator located at the north pole of the central bubble, at the north pole of the cortex. In these faces are inscribed circles and all the circles are in fact circular discs and not equal, as if they are in one seat of the normal polyhedron corresponding to the n world, n seats. in its diameter, it gives a small thickness of parable, with a camshaft very small. The parable is almost flat, with a little thickness in the center of the disk, and this disk, which touches the spherical oscillator, is on a common basis of universes corresponding to all the worlds created.

Common base corresponding to each universe, of these worlds and the disks inscribed of the seats of regular polyhedra. And the common base, better disks corresponding to universes of different worlds, tangential to the spherical oscillator and outlined in the crust (the polyhedron to which they belong) . And as common-ordinary records, sought after!

Re-see the shape of the central bubble with the spherical oscillator, its center the control center of the universes and an E plane that touches the south pole. The spherical oscillator in a time much shorter than the period of the hydrogen atom, transmits to the center of control and this to all universes, the laws that are governed by them and their movement flows deterministically.

IN THE TWO-DIMENSIONAL REAL SPACE x,y

The above means that when we have $y = x + iz$ and $x = y + iz$ and $y - x = x - y = 0$ so $(y - x)^2 = -z^2$. Kai $iz = (y - x)$. Then we are led to that $(y - x) - iz = 0$. But we can also get it equal to the unit, since zero is also one, since the complex number $z_{xy} = (y - x) - iz = 1$ of the two dimensions is what corresponds to the single dimensional real space (the 2 dimensions it is, $x - y, i z$, t both x,y, they are of the real space that now become one or x-y)

$$\text{with}^4 = 1 = [(x - y) + iz]^4$$

z_{zx}, z_{zy} , are complex numbers

Remember the number $z = r(\cos 2k\pi/n + i \sin 2k\pi/n) = r e^{2k\pi i/n}$, $k=1,2,3,\dots,n-1$, which has root $\omega = \cos 2\pi/n + i \sin 2\pi/n$ representing a radius inscribed in a circle. The number $-x + y - iz = 0 = 1$ and it is as if we have a two-dimensional complex number $z = d + iz = 1$. Here, in the radius there is the real, the imaginary and the real and the imaginary time, the 4 dimensions.

³ COMPLEX VARIABLES M. Mirror, Sna. 5

THE WORLD OF THE THREE DIMENSIONS OF SPACE WITH A TIME DIMENSION AND THE THREE IMAGINARY DIMENSIONS OF SPACE AND ONE OF TIME

A regular tetrahedron, one of Plato's regular polyhedra, is also, within the central bubble, inscribed in its cortex.

It has edge a , the circumscribed radius R of the crust in the tetrahedron, is $R = a\sqrt{6}/4$. And the sphere of the central bubble, is the 6dimensional world and corresponds to the normal tetrahedron (4 equilateral triangles). Each triangle has a recorded circle, corresponding to a universe of this world. And each universe has the two dimensions of space, it is flat. And in each plane universe of a layer of bubbles, the number $z_{xy} = (y-x) - iz = 1$ also corresponds, as in the plane we analyzed. But the complex numbers of the seats of the tetrahedron, are vectors that correspond to the three-dimensional coordinate system of space. And so we will have three complex, with three imaginary axes, $z_{xy} = (y-x) - iz = 1$ $z_{xz} = (y-z) - iz = 1$ and $z_{yz} = (z-x) - iz = 1$. Therefore, the space of 4edron, is a space of two dimensions for each universe-circle of real space, a radial dimension of time, because the movement is of variation of the radius of the spherical wave and three fictitious hesitations, the imaginary space is three-dimensional with the dimension of imaginary time in addition.

The central bubble is the basis of the existence of worlds, one and two of space and the dimension (monodimensionality) of time, with the corresponding imaginary dimensions. Inside the bubble, there are no worlds of three dimensions of space and one of time, there are 6two-dimensional worlds (triangles), where the two dimensions of the surface correspond to the corresponding two imaginary and in addition the two dimensions of real and imaginary time.

IN THE THREE DIMENSIONS OF THE SPACE

In the three stretches, the movement of the ether in densities-dilutions, linear, surface and volume, is unique. Time is movement and unit of time uniformly repetitive motion. In all three dimensions we have the dimension of time, only that time (the thickening-dilution of the ether), always occurs linearly-radially, time is one-dimensional!

In the three dimensions of space, we consider within the central bubble, a two-dimensional system of convoluted z, x, y and, $x = R\cos\theta, z = R\sin\theta$ if R is located on the axes x, z and the complex number again z is,

$$z = x + iz = R(\cos\theta + i\sin\theta) \text{ και } \text{from} = z - x \quad (1)$$

If we keep $x = R\cos\theta$ constant in the three-dimensional real space x, y, z and rotate it around the z -axis, then a circle is formed with its center on the z -axis and a radius $r < R$, with a plane parallel to x, y . The $r = x = R\cos\theta$, and $r^2 = x^2 + y^2$, at the level x, y . If we select our actions correctly (we also rotate the axes), then the radius circle r is located at the level of one of the seats of the tetrahedron.

THE WORLD OF THE TETRAHEDRON

A correspond to it 4 universes, of 4 sides of the normal 4seat, which is inscribed 4edron in the circle of the crust of the bubble.

In the center of the bubble, a small sphere of dense ether corresponds itself and receives the influence of the spherical oscillator located at the north pole of the bubble and affects the control center of the universes. that gushes energy from scratch. The variation of the radius is very small, and thickenings and dilutions occur that propagate in the elastic ether. Part of the thickenings is reflected from the cortex and part spreads to the outer ether, enosis. In this next space is the 12dimensional world (with the three dimensions of plane and time and imaginary three dimensions of plane and the three dimensions of time) and the 12dimensional with the 6 sq. acorner of the cube, which is described).

THE DISK OF THE THREE REAL DIMENSIONS OF SPACE

The diametrical incision of the disc is narrow in thickness,

Incision of a diametrically circular disk, it is about a flat

The equation of ellipse is, $r=p/(1-ecos \theta)$ and when its eccentricity e approaches the unit, then the ellipse approaches the level, since it is not a unit, it is in two dimensions of space the lack and the disk in three. To such disks correspond the universes of the worlds, which are their polyhedrons outlined in the crust of the central bubble

In the disk universes, space is anisotropic and non-homogeneous, that is, the movement of a material point in the three dimensions does not have the same behavior and the density of the ether changes; in the center of gravity of the ellipse it is denser and dilutes along its two axes. , it is smaller on the horizontal axis and larger on the vertical. But the density ρ is not linear along the axes. Thus, a rectilinear radiation that reaches the earth, where the earth is at the center of the axes of the ellipse and the vertical diameter in the ellipse, of the disk, may in fact not be rectilinear .

THE CUBE OUR WORLD

The cube has an edge a , and the cube that has the ball of the crust of the central bubble inscribed, corresponds to our world with $a/2=R$.

We will do something similar to the 6dimensional world, within the bubble. We consider a coordinate system x, y, z , of the central bubble; we consider the axis z , axis of imaginary numbers z . We consider , $z=r\sin\theta$ and $x=r\cos\theta$, $r>R$.

$$z=x+iz=r(\cos\theta+isin\theta)$$

We keep the $r\cos\theta$ constant and rotate around the axis z the $r\sin\theta$. Then the angle θ is of the original vector, but now it is $x^2+z^2=r'^2$ and r is the projection of r' , at the plane x, y . And $x=r'\cos\phi$ and ϕ the angle of r, r'

Vector r' , rotates around the axis z with a radius $r'\cos\theta=r$, and r equal to the central bubble and forms a circle corresponding to a disk of one of the 6 universes of our world.

One disk is of our universe, which corresponds to the cube of our world and has 6 universes-disks with a small thickness, in each seat of the cube and three-dimensional time.

In our world we can have a rectilinear motion of 3dimensional, which in the three-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system, is,

$$x=x_0+v_1\Delta t \quad y=y_0+v_2\Delta t \quad z=z_0+v_3\Delta t$$

$$\kappa\alpha \Delta t=(x-x_0)/v_1=(y-y_0)/v_2=(z-z_0)/v_3$$

the three same tenses corresponding to the three dimensions of the space. The one-dimensional time is a vector, the three-dimensional is the scalar volume of the three vectors, it is Dt^3 and it is a scalar magnitude. our dimensional world, depicted by complex numbers that are vectors. And in the axes x,y,z , the imaginary ix, iy, iz correspond. And do not forget, that time, one-dimensional time is movement, uniformly repetitive movement unit of time.

In the one-dimensional real world the motion made in the real world is on the radius R ($R=R_0+vt$) and the imaginary world on iR and respectively the times $Dt=(R-R_0)/v$, $Dt_i=(R_i-R_{oi})/v$ (4 dimensions in fact). In the 6-dimensional world of the two real dimensions, R , is in the two dimensions of the circle. The other two imaginary and time, because Dt is the same, we do not distinguish it, so we have only two dimensions of time.

WHAT IS MOVEMENT

The displacement of a material object in space is movement. And because the displacement corresponds to two AB points in space, then it corresponds to a vector $\mathbf{AB}=\mathbf{Dx}$, if it is located on the axis x (and $\mathbf{AB}=\Delta\mathbf{x} +\Delta\mathbf{y} +\Delta\mathbf{z}$ at 3 dimensions)." This shift AB, occurs in time Δt . Δt is motion-displacement in space and here where the movement is rectilinear, we will have, $\Delta\mathbf{t}_1 +\Delta\mathbf{t}_2 +\Delta\mathbf{t}_3 =3\Delta t = \Delta t_1\mathbf{e}_1+ \Delta t_2\mathbf{e}_2+ \Delta t_3\mathbf{e}_3 =$ the three dimensions of time, to which the imaginary correspond.

And $\Delta t_1=\Delta t_2=\Delta t_3$ with $\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3$ the unit vectors, and corresponding to the vectors $\Delta\mathbf{x} + \Delta\mathbf{y} +\Delta\mathbf{z}$.

But in a very advanced analysis, because the real space the three-dimensional is anisotropic and heterogeneous, then the three tenses Δt , are not equal and that is why we consider them three dimensions of our world and not one, as in the real one-dimensional and two-dimensional world.

Then the velocity is $v= \Delta\mathbf{x}_i /\Delta\mathbf{t}_i$ is a scalar magnitude, it is a measure of motion and the acceleration vector. And the magnetic moment will now be, $\boldsymbol{\mu}=\mathbf{IA}=\mathbf{evr}/2$. That is, they are constant, but vectors. And the force $\mathbf{F}=\mathbf{mv}^2/\mathbf{r}=\mathbf{mv}^2\mathbf{r}^4/\mathbf{r}^3$ is a vector, like acceleration. When the central force is inverse to the radius of the two bodies in the cube, then the angular momentum and the magnetic momentum of the particle are constant.

In the world of twelve dimensions are the universes (3 real dimensions of space, 3 imaginary dimensions of space, 3 real dimensions of time and 3 imaginary) like our universe, $z^{12}=1$ and its root corresponding to $z= \omega=\cos 2\pi/12 +i\sin 2\pi/12$, corresponds to a normal cube.

THE WORLD OF 12 DIMENSIONS OF NORMAL OCTAHEDRON

Our world of 6 universes corresponds to the 12 dimensions of spacetime and 6 sides of the cube.

The normal octahedron has 8 equilateral triangles and equal to each other. It has inscribed sphere the central bubble radius $r=(6^{1/2}/6)a$, a =edge. Circumscribed sphere radius $R=(2^{1/2}/2)a > R_6$ of our own world, with an edge of a normal triangle a.

The octahedron is two quadrilateral pyramids based on a common square. On this common base, the two dimensions of time occur, and on the triangles, the three dimensions of space and 3 of time.

The spherical densities-dilutions of the ether, which cross the disks-universes, which are inscribed in the 8 triangles and have the three dimensions of the space, as in our cube-world, and the octahedron takes the square as the common base of its two pyramids. that there are the two dimensions of time, from where it takes the two-dimensional time.

For this world of 12 dimensions, it is, $z^{12}=1$, which has as roots $z= \omega=\cos 2\pi/12 +i\sin 2\pi/12$, corresponding to a normal 12-gon, as in our world of the cube.

THE WORLD OF 18 DIMENSIONS

Plato's next regular polyhedron is the normal 12edros. It has 12 seats regular pentagons, and each pentagon has a recorded small thickness radius disc r, and due to the thickness it has the three dimensions of the space.

The 12hedron is circumscribed in the sphere of the crust of the central bubble, with radius, $R=\{(3)^{1/2}/2\}\varphi a=\{(3)^{1/2}/4\}\{1+(5)^{1/2}\}a$, a =edge of the seat of a regular polygon and φ =golden number. And it has the sphere of the crust inscribed, with radius $r=\{\varphi^2/(2(3)^{1/2}-\varphi)\}a$

Space corresponds to the movement of the material body, which has the three dimensions of space and the 3 of time corresponding to the creator God with the corresponding three imaginaries of time, but also the three dimensions of time corresponding to the distant zero and the other three imaginary, a total of 18 dimensions. The Δt_1 vector of time has a projection at the symmetry plane of 12hedron.

In the world of the 12-seater, the ulterior reality has zero! So this intervenes in this world and this is done with three dimensions of time belonging to it and the other influence is made with the three dimensions of time, which belong to the Goddess creator. Thus, in the original coordinate system of space, there are on its three semi-axes, systems of coordinates of time, real and imaginary time, belonging to the distant zero and the goddess.

Coordinate system of space, the axes correspond to two systems of coordinates of time, as in the figure corresponds to the axis x

In each semi-axis of coordinates correspond two systems of coordinates of time, and each one belongs to the Goddess, and the other distant zero. In the negative semi-axes of space, correspond coordinate systems of imaginary time. each axis of time that is parallel to the others, has the same vector of the time of motion performed in the coordinate system of space. , they belong to equal corresponding dimensions of time, but they come from both, they are the same, but two kinds of dimensions, So we have the 3 dimensions of space and the corresponding 3 imaginary, the 3 dimensions real of the time of the Goddess and the corresponding imaginary and the 3 of the outer zero real and the 3 corresponding imaginary (18 dimensions).

The number is $z^{18}=1$ and has roots $z = \omega = \cos 2\pi/18 + i \sin 2\pi/18$, corresponding to the 18 vertices, of normal tenoctagon.

The 12hedron has a registered sphere R of the crust, $R = \frac{\phi^3 a}{2(3-\phi)^{1/2}}$ and circumscribed $r = \frac{3^{1/2} \phi a}{2} = \frac{3^{1/2}(1+5^{1/2})a}{4}$.

THE WORLD OF 24 DIMENSIONS

It corresponds to Plato's canonical 20hedro, with twenty regular triangles corresponding to the twenty universes.

The 20-drshall be described in the central bubble and shall have a radius,

$$R = \frac{a}{2} \{ \phi(5)^{1/2} \}^{1/2} = \frac{1}{4} \{ 10 + 2(5)^{1/2} \}^{1/2} a$$

a= length of a triangle edge. And inscribed the sphere of the central bubble with a radius

$$r = \frac{\phi^2 a}{2(3)^{1/2}}$$

In the 20edros there are the dimensions of the 12-seater with an additional three of the year, which are waiting for man to be deified, to influence the Whole and to direct them. These are,

Coordinate system of space, the axes correspond to three systems of coordinates of time, as in the figure corresponds to the axis x

In the figure, the 3 real dimensions of space correspond to the 3 imaginary dimensions of space and there are three by three 9 dimensions of time, with the corresponding imaginary ones (in the figure they must be represented on the negative semi-axes), ie $18 + 6 = 24$ dimensions. The 6 dimensions of time belong to man, this world was not yet created.

THE HOLOGRAMS OF THE UNIVERSES

The worlds located outside the central bubble, 12 in size and above), have universes that are circular disks, of minimal thickness. These universes are holograms.

In fact there are these circular universes at the depth of the whole, which radiate monochromatic radiation. there are synapses of atoms that radiate, and the radiation of these atoms falls very laterally into the cyclic beam of radiation of the universes. , of small thickness and abut some on the oscillator located at the north pole of the central bubble.

3. SUMMARY

The structure of the Whole is briefly described and is what TOTALITARIAN THEORY brings. There is a one-dimensional, two-dimensional and three-dimensional world of real dimensions. Behind them there are the imaginary space, but there are also the dimensions of time, real and imaginary. Simple motion determines the time Dt , which is the same in all three dimensions of a movement.

While space has three dimensions with the corresponding imaginary ones, time, as defined, has the three dimensions with the corresponding imaginary ones belonging to the goddess and so many others that belong to the ultimate reality. It is the world of 18 dimensions.

Finally, it remains to create the world of 24 dimensions, which will have in addition to the dimensions of the time of the goddess and which will have a distant zero and another six that will belong to the man who will become a creator

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